

Original Article

Modeling the Short Run and Long Run Impact of consumption of Non-Renewable Energy and Renewable Energy on Economic Growth in Pakistan: A VECM Analysis

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Abstract

Renewable energy is a key factor in expanding access to energy and electricity through the continual rise of renewable power generation. Air pollution and energy poverty are taking lives, causing suffering, and impeding progress. The aim of the study is to ensure that energy is modern, affordable, sustainable, and dependable. For this study, the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) is applied along with Granger causality testing to scrutinize both short-run and long-run relationships among non-renewable energy consumption (NREC), renewable energy consumption (REC), labor force (LFOR), gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), and economic growth (GDP), covering the period 1990 to 2023. A key strength of this work lies in applying VECM for analyzing macroeconomic relationships over different time horizons. The findings for Pakistan reveal that REC and NREC positively and significantly affect long-run GDP, despite LFOR exerting an insignificant effect, and GFCF shows a negative statistically significant relationship with economic growth. Granger causality results indicate a bidirectional relationship between GDP and REC, a unidirectional flow from GFCF to GDP, and from GDP to LFOR, with no causal link detected between GDP and NREC.

JEL: C32, O44, Q42, Q43, Q48

Keywords: Economic Growth, Renewable Energy Consumption, Non-Renewable Energy Consumption, Vector Error Correction Model.

Introduction

Economic growth is the rate at which the economy's potential production rises over time. A country's national income will rise in tandem with economic growth. Individuals, the economy, and the environment can all benefit from economic expansion. Natural resources are one of the main drivers of economic progress because a country with abundant natural resources may manufacture goods and services at lower costs. Our way of life and all economic activity are based on natural resources. Both developed and developing economies have significant challenges in their economic development because to their depletion. Their effective utilization is a requisite condition and should be the objective of public policies enacted by governments globally (Singh et al., 2024). Renewable resources such as sunlight and wind, replenish more quickly than they deplete and resources that are not renewable include coal, oil, natural gas, and fossil fuels.

Energy is an essential component of economic activity. For sustainability and to boost GDP growth, the energy industry must be stable and effective. For energy in particular, most societies rely significantly on non-renewable resources. The negative social and environmental effects of investing in non-renewable resources are a major drawback. In recent years, the increasing trend of carbon emissions and the detrimental consequences of climate

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change on social and economic activities have become significant issues (Amin et al., 2023). The energy crisis is the most significant global issue that has an impact on Pakistan in particular, affecting the country's social, economic, and environmental well-being. One of the countries experiencing electricity shortages is Pakistan, where nuclear and renewable energy sources contribute very little to economic growth. In addition, fewer than half of rural residents have no or extremely inadequate access to power, making it a significant challenge for both rural and urban populations (Luqman et al., 2019).

There is a significant disparity between the supply as well as demand of energy in developing countries. Due to their limited energy supplies and the adverse impact of imports on their balance of payments, developing nations' industries' energy use drives up energy costs (Safdar et al., 2019).

Pakistan's economic and industrial development are still heavily influenced by the energy sector, which also has an effect on trade competitiveness, productivity, and overall quality of life. With the help of large investments in wind and solar energy, Pakistan's energy sector is making significant progress toward switching from imported fossil fuels to renewable energy sources. A favorable shift toward renewable and environmentally benign energy sources is seen in Pakistan's production of 90,145 GWh from July to March of FY 2025, of which 53.7% came from nuclear, hydel, and renewable sources. [Government of Pakistan, Economic Survey (2024-2025)].

The remaining portions of the paper are as follows: The literature review is discussed in section 2, and data, methodology, and a discussion of the findings are provided in section 3. The final section consists of a conclusion and policy recommendations.

Research Questions

This study examines whether a long-run relationship exists between economic growth and key macroeconomic factors in Pakistan, such as the labor force, gross fixed capital formation, and energy consumption (both renewable and nonrenewable). Therefore, the on the basis of existing literature review the research question and objectives are:

1. What are the effects of long-run variations in Pakistan's labor force, energy consumption (both renewable and nonrenewable) and gross fixed capital formation have on economic growth?
2. What are the effects of short-run variations in Pakistan's labor force, energy consumption (both renewable and nonrenewable) and gross fixed capital formation have on economic growth?
3. What is the causal relationship between economic growth and macroeconomic variables?

Objectives of the Study

1. To investigate the long-run equilibrium relationship between macroeconomic factors, such as Pakistan's labor force, gross fixed capital formation, energy consumption (both renewable and nonrenewable), and economic growth.
2. To evaluate the short-term dynamics and their impact on economic growth in relation to the selected macroeconomic variables.
3. To identify the granger causal relationship between economic growth and macroeconomic variables.

Literature Review

Derouez et.al (2024) analyzed Saudi Arabia between 1990 and 2022, incorporating a broad set of variables such as renewable and non-renewable energy, technology, foreign direct investment (FDI), energy export, energy price, CO₂ emissions, and population. Using ARDL and VECM approaches, the study found that both renewable and non-renewable energy, along with FDI, energy price, energy export, and population, supported growth. However, technological progress and CO₂ emissions negatively influenced it. Bidirectional causality was identified between growth, non-renewables, FDI, energy prices and energy exports, suggesting important policy lessons around energy diversification and human capital development.

Mohammadi et al. (2023) examined how renewable and non-renewable energy consumption shaped economic growth across developed and developing countries between 1993 and 2019. Applying panel cointegration and causality tests, they found that energy consumption significantly and positively drives growth. Interestingly, renewable energy provided a “protection effect” in developed nations, reinforcing

growth resilience, whereas in developing countries, a feedback effect emerged, suggesting that cutting energy use could threaten their economic expansion.

Amin et al. (2023) shifted focus to Pakistan, using household-level PLSM 2018–2019 survey data and the STIRPAT model to analyze the links between household size, income, renewable and non-renewable energy, biomass, and carbon footprint. Their findings revealed a nuanced dynamic: rising income initially increased emissions but later contributed to reductions, while larger household sizes consistently heightened emissions. Non-renewable energy and biomass were strong drivers of higher carbon outputs, whereas renewable energy had a modest but negative effect in rural areas. The study emphasized that expanding renewables could serve as a pathway toward reducing emissions and achieving sustainability.

Extending the scope of renewable energy sources, Durrani et al. (2022) examined hydroelectricity, nuclear energy, fossil fuels, labor, and capital in Pakistan from 1972 to 2015. Their analysis revealed bidirectional causality between GDP and capital formation and a feedback loop between fossil fuels and growth. In contrast, hydroelectricity and nuclear energy showed a unidirectional impact on GDP, pointing to the importance of diversifying renewable energy resources.

Similarly, Asif et al. (2022) explored energy options in Pakistan by comparing the costs, yields, and environmental implications of agricultural waste energy, nuclear power, and fossil fuels. Their results highlighted agricultural waste-based bioenergy as a cost-effective and environmentally friendly alternative to nuclear energy, advocating for stronger adoption of renewables to address Pakistan's energy crisis.

Jan et al. (2021) analyzed Pakistan (1972–2015) through ARDL with structural break tests, confirming cointegration among energy consumption, GDP, and other variables. Both renewable and non-renewable energy sources supported economic growth, but renewable energy had a stronger effect, indicating that it is more efficient as a driver of economic expansion.

Polat (2021) compared developing and developed economies (2002–2014), applying dynamic panel methods. The results indicated that non-renewable energy fueled growth in developing countries but had no significant role in developed ones, while renewable energy did not yield strong effects in advanced economies either. These findings highlight the heterogeneity of the energy growth nexus across income groups.

Majeed et al. (2021) provided a global perspective by examining 174 economies from 1980 to 2019. They disaggregated renewables into biomass, solar, wind, and hydro, they found that overall renewables spurred growth worldwide. Non-renewables, however, boosted growth only in developing countries and hindered it in advanced ones. Among renewables, biomass and solar had strong positive effects, while wind and hydro displayed mixed results. The study also noted that capital formation encouraged growth, whereas population growth exerted a dampening effect. While inflation lowers growth in developing economies, it increases it in developed economies.

Looking at Myanmar, Ahmed et al. (2019) investigated the roles of renewable energy, non-renewable energy, labor force, and CO₂ intensity in shaping economic growth from 1990 to 2016. Results highlighted the growth-promoting role of renewables, while non-renewables hindered growth, largely due to technological inefficiencies. Labor force participation, meanwhile, provided a positive contribution.

Luqman et al. (2019) focused on Pakistan (1990–2016) and applied nonlinear ARDL to explore renewable and nuclear energy effects. The findings show that both positive and negative shocks to nuclear and renewable energy variables will boost economic expansion, with capital also contributing positively. However, oil consumption reduced renewable energy use, while oil prices showed neutral effects. This suggests renewable and nuclear energy as sustainable pathways for growth.

At the regional level, Soava et al. (2018) analyzed 28 EU countries (1995–2015) and concluded that renewable energy generally boosts growth, with evidence of both bidirectional and unidirectional causality depending on the country context. The rising share of renewables in final energy consumption across the EU was taken as further justification for EU policies favoring clean energy.

Focusing on Tunisia, Ben Mbarek et al. (2018) investigated the interplay between energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, and growth from 1990 to 2015 using cointegration and VECM causality tests. They reported a bidirectional relationship between energy use and CO₂ emissions, as well as a unidirectional causality from

energy consumption to growth in the short run. The findings position renewable energy as a critical enabler for sustainable development.

Similarly, Gozgor et al. (2018) studied 29 OECD countries (1990–2013) using panel ARDL and quantile regression approaches. Their findings underscored that both renewable and non-renewable energy, alongside greater economic complexity, contributed positively to growth, pointing to the importance of diversification and structural capabilities.

Adams et al. (2018) assessed the influence of regime type and energy consumption, encompassing both renewable and non-renewable sources, on economic growth in 30 Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries from 1980 to 2012. The results indicated that both renewable and non-renewable energy can help the economy grow, although non-renewable energy has a bigger effect on growth than renewable energy. When all other things are equal, economic growth increases by 0.27% for every 10% increase in the use of renewable energy and by 2.11% for the use of non-renewable energy.

Khoshnevis Yazdi and Shakouri (2017), in contrast, found different results for Iran (1979–2014). Using ARDL and Granger causality, they showed that renewable energy negatively affected GDP in both the short and long term. Causality tests revealed a unidirectional link from renewable energy to GDP, implying that economic growth plays a role in fostering renewable energy development rather than being driven by it.

For Pakistan, Shahbaz et al. (2015) examined quarterly data from 1972 to 2011 using ARDL and rolling window techniques. They confirmed long-term cointegration between renewable energy, capital, labor, and GDP. Both renewables and conventional production factors enhanced growth, while Granger causality tests pointed to a feedback relationship among renewable energy and economic growth.

In a broader OECD context, Apergis and Payne (2010) studied 20 countries (1985–2005) using panel cointegration and error correction models. Their investigation revealed a long-run equilibrium in which renewable energy significantly supported growth. Granger causality tests further revealed bidirectional causality between renewables and growth in both the short and long run, indicating a reinforcing relationship.

Methodology and Data Sources

The analysis explores the relationship among economic growth and crucial macroeconomic factors in Pakistan. The annual data is from the World Development Indicators (WDI) from 1990 to 2023. This study employs various tests, including unit root analysis (ADF), Johansen co-integration, the VECM, and Granger causality. Diagnostic tests are performed to ensure the validity, reliability, and robustness of econometric models.

Conceptual Framework

The study includes four independent variables: gross fixed capital formation, energy consumption (both renewable and non-renewable), and labor force, as well as one dependent variable, economic growth, to scrutinize the short-run and long-run relationship between these variables. To shed light on these relationships, we developed a model inspired by the work of Majeed et al. (2021); Jan et al. (2021) & Dogan (2015).

Model Specification

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 REC + \beta_2 NREC + \beta_3 GFCF + \beta_4 LFOR + \mu_i \quad (1)$$

Whereas β_0 denotes the intercept, the parameters that need to be estimated are the coefficients β_1 to β_4 . μ_i represents the error term, GDP represents economic growth, REC denotes the renewable energy consumption, NREC, GFCF, and LFOR represent the non-renewable energy consumption, gross fixed capital formation and labor force in the model. The study hypotheses are as follows:

Hypotheses

H₁: Renewable and non-renewable energy consumption, gross fixed capital formation, labor force has significant long-run impacts on economic growth in Pakistan.

H₂: Macroeconomic variables such as REC, NREC, LFOR and GFCF Granger-cause GDP in the short run.

Table: 1 Variable Description

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Unit</i>
Economic Growth	GDP	Constant 2015 US\$
Labor Force	LFOR	Labor force participation rate, total (% of total population ages 15+) (modeled ILO estimate)
Renewable Energy Consumption	REC	% of total final energy consumption
Non-Renewable Energy Consumption	NREC	Kg of oil equivalent per capita
Gross Fixed Capital Formation	GFCF	Constant 2015 US\$

Estimation and Analysis of Empirical Findings

The econometric analysis's findings are presented in this section along with a suitable interpretation. Descriptive data are presented first, followed by the findings' outcomes.

Descriptive Analysis

EViews displays the descriptive analyses that define the raw data in Table 2. The Jarque-Bera test findings show that all of the variables are normally distributed.

Table: 2 Descriptive Analysis

	<i>GDP</i>	<i>REC</i>	<i>NREC</i>	<i>GFCF</i>	<i>LFOR</i>
<i>Mean</i>	2.33E+11	48.516	421.186	3.44E+10	50.620
<i>Median</i>	2.28E+11	47.650	420.455	3.45E+10	50.493
<i>Maximum</i>	4.00E+11	58.100	455.174	5.50E+10	52.730
<i>Minimum</i>	1.10E+11	41.600	366.397	2.05E+10	48.360
<i>Std. Dev.</i>	9.06E+10	4.543	24.486	1.00E+10	1.039
<i>Skewness</i>	0.396	0.310	-0.537	0.298	0.172

Source: Author's Estimation

Stationarity test

This stage involves determining and verifying the stationary nature of the time series data. It may be inferred from Table 3's ADF test results for GDP, REC, NREC, GFCF, and LFOR that the null hypothesis is not rejected. Accordingly, we lack sufficient evidence to rule out the possibility that the data are nonstationary. According to the analysis below, the GDP, REC, NREC, GFCF, and LFOR time series data are all nonstationary. Using the differencing procedure and the first differencing findings ($d=1$), the data is made stationary. Furthermore, the ADF stationarity test results, which are compiled in Table 4, demonstrate that every variable is stationary.

Table 3: Result of the Unit Root

ADF Unit Root Test at Level			
Variable	t-Statistic	Prob.*	
GDP	2.080	1.000	Non-Stationary
REC	-1.399	0.571	Non-Stationary
NREC	-1.828	0.361	Non-Stationary
GFCF	-1.258	0.637	Non-Stationary
LFOR	-0.831	0.797	Non-Stationary

Source: Author's Estimation

Table 4: Result of the Unit Root

ADF Unit Root Test at First Difference			
Variable	t-Statistic	Prob.*	
GDP	-4.295	0.002	Stationary
REC	-5.697	0.000	Stationary
NREC	-4.946	0.000	Stationary
GFCF	-3.445	0.017	Stationary
LFOR	-6.512	0.000	Stationary

Source: Author's Estimation

Choosing the Vector-Autoregression (VAR) Order

Determining the optimum lag length for the next testing phase is the main objective of the optimal lag determination process. Avoiding autocorrelation problems in the test data is yet another objective. In this study, lag is determined using the AIC approach. The optimal lag test provided the following results in table 5.

Table 5: VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1770.173	NA	1.05E+42	110.948	111.177	111.024
1	-1633.988	221.301	1.03E+39	103.999	105.3734*	104.455
2	-1597.640	47.70735*	5.74e+38*	103.2900*	105.809	104.1250*

Source: Author's Estimation

Examine Cointegration and Long-Term Relationships

After selecting the optimal lag length, the Johansen cointegration test was applied using both trace and max-eigenvalue statistics. The Trace test indicated three cointegrating equations among the variables, while the Max-Eigenvalue test suggested one cointegrating equation. We rejected the null hypothesis of no cointegration since both statistics were higher than their critical values.

Table 6: Johansen's Co-integration (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.808	105.572	69.819	0.000
At most 1 *	0.546	54.488	47.856	0.011
At most 2 *	0.488	29.995	29.797	0.047
At most 3	0.189	9.263	15.495	0.342
At most 4	0.086	2.784	3.841	0.095

Source: Author's Estimation

Table 7: Johansen's Co-integration (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.808	51.085	33.877	0.000
At most 1	0.546	24.493	27.584	0.118
At most 2	0.488	20.732	21.132	0.057
At most 3	0.189	6.479	14.265	0.553
At most 4	0.086	2.784	3.841	0.095

Source: Author's Estimation

According to tables 6 and 7, the cointegrated equations allow us to move further with the VECM model. The dependent and independent variables' short-run and long-run casualties are tested with the help of this model. The REC, NREC, LFOR, and GFCF are independent variables in this study; economic growth is the dependent variable.

The coefficients of REC and NREC in the cointegration equation (CointEq) are positive and statistically significant with t-statistics (REC = 3.31705 and NREC = 2.48135), suggesting that the consumption of non-renewable energy and renewable energy is related to the long-run increase in economic growth. These results are in line with (Jan et al., 2021). Although the GFCF coefficient has a negative significant value ($t = -3.71403$). These results are consistent with (Dauda and Abdulkareem, 2023). Conversely, the LFOR coefficient is insignificant ($t = -1.48586$). The similar result was previously observed by (Jan et al., 2021) in their earlier investigation in Pakistan.

Table 8 displays the outcomes of the short-run dynamics. According to the findings, the estimate of ECM_{t-1} is -0.054 and statistically significant ($t = -3.37462$). This suggests that variations in the short run toward the long-run equilibrium adjust for 5.4% of differences in economic growth. With the exception of $D(GFCF(-1))$, which exerts a positive and statistically significant influence on economic growth ($t = 2.43850$), all factors are inconsequential in a short period of time. The VECM results are explained in detail in Table 8

Table 8 Vector Error Correction Estimates (VECM)

Cointegrating Eq:	CointEq1
GDP(-1)	1.000000
REC(-1)	4.83E+10 (1.5E+10) [3.31705]
NREC(-1)	4.35E+09 (1.8E+09) [2.48135]
GFCF(-1)	-7.391271 (1.99010) [-3.71403]
LFOR(-1)	-2.68E+10 (1.8E+10) [-1.48586]

C					
-2.79E+12					
Error Correction:	D(GDP)	D(REC)	D(NREC)	D(GFCF)	D(LFOR)
CointEq1	-0.054159 (0.01605) [-3.37462]	-6.18E-12 (4.7E-12) [-1.32120]	5.38E-11 (3.0E-11) [1.78258]	0.002148 (0.01109) [0.19373]	-1.15E-13 (1.7E-12) [-0.06932]
D(GDP(-1))	-0.472696 (0.28872) [-1.63721]	-8.14E-11 (8.4E-11) [-0.96798]	9.48E-10 (5.4E-10) [1.74670]	0.126663 (0.19943) [0.63513]	6.51E-12 (3.0E-11) [0.21805]
D(GDP(-2))	-0.474319 (0.28748) [-1.64993]	-7.34E-11 (8.4E-11) [-0.87672]	5.53E-10 (5.4E-10) [1.02411]	-0.067741 (0.19857) [-0.34114]	1.36E-11 (3.0E-11) [0.45907]
D(REC(-1))	1.35E+08 (1.2E+09) [0.11012]	-0.004010 (0.35656) [-0.01125]	-1.615406 (2.30079) [-0.70211]	-1.18E+09 (8.5E+08) [-1.39983]	-0.079668 (0.12655) [-0.62954]
D(REC(-2))	8.71E+08 (9.6E+08) [0.90382]	-0.638896 (0.28067) [-2.27634]	1.147950 (1.81111) [0.63384]	6.44E+08 (6.7E+08) [0.96738]	0.188814 (0.09962) [1.89542]
D(NREC(-1))	2.70E+08 (2.1E+08) [1.29404]	-0.000920 (0.06086) [-0.01511]	-0.225703 (0.39275) [-0.57468]	-50047545 (1.4E+08) [-0.34669]	-0.026001 (0.02160) [-1.20361]
D(NREC(-2))	2.56E+08 (1.5E+08) [1.74269]	-0.068499 (0.04274) [-1.60264]	-0.075311 (0.27580) [-0.27306]	1.69E+08 (1.0E+08) [1.67170]	0.011751 (0.01517) [0.77459]
D(GFCF(-1))	1.118604 (0.45873) [2.43850]	-1.74E-11 (1.3E-10) [-0.13044]	3.34E-10 (8.6E-10) [0.38749]	0.082461 (0.31686) [0.26024]	1.17E-11 (4.7E-11) [0.24609]
D(GFCF(-2))	-0.590402 (0.48921) [-1.20685]	1.30E-10 (1.4E-10) [0.91330]	-1.84E-09 (9.2E-10) [-2.00675]	-0.192058 (0.33792) [-0.56836]	-7.55E-11 (5.1E-11) [-1.49211]
D(LFOR(-1))	-1.61E+09 (2.3E+09) [-0.68965]	-0.842426 (0.67934) [-1.24007]	-3.695271 (4.38365) [-0.84297]	1.31E+08 (1.6E+09) [0.08112]	-0.087787 (0.24111) [-0.36409]
D(LFOR(-2))	-1.69E+09 (2.1E+09) [-0.81479]	-0.196416 (0.60396) [-0.32521]	-1.209815 (3.89727) [-0.31043]	-2.09E+09 (1.4E+09) [-1.45685]	-0.440588 (0.21436) [-2.05535]
C	1.63E+10 (4.3E+09) [3.78829]	0.780634 (1.25429) [0.62237]	-8.883535 (8.09375) [-1.09758]	-2.33E+08 (3.0E+09) [-0.07828]	0.120859 (0.44518) [0.27148]

Source: Author's Estimation

The Wald test was employed to look into the short-run relationship between the variables. As shown in table 9 evidence of short-run causality is found among GDP and the GFCF because the probability value is less than 0.05. We conclude that no short-run relationship exists between GDP and LFOR, REC, and NREC as the probability values of these variables exceed the 5% significance level.

Table 9: VEC Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald Tests

Dependent variable: D(GDP)			
Excluded	Chi-sq	Df	Prob.
D(REC)	0.825	2	0.662
D(NREC)	4.042	2	0.133
D(GFCF)	8.347	2	0.015
D(LFOR)	1.226	2	0.542

Source: Author's Estimation

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

The findings of the causality test are shown in table 10. The causal relationship GDP and REC. The results indicate a bidirectional causality relationship between GDP and the REC; the decision rule H_0 is rejected because the probability value is less than 0.05. The results then also demonstrate that the relationship between GFCF and GDP is unidirectional. However, there is a causal relationship in that GFCF affects GDP. Additionally, the relationship between LFOR and GDP is unidirectional, meaning that LFOR is affected by GDP. Lastly, there was no causality between GDP and NREC; the decision rule H_0 is accepted since the probability value is more than 0.05.

Table: 10 Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
REC does not Granger Cause GDP	32	5.84163	0.0078
GDP does not Granger Cause REC		3.87791	0.0331
NREC does not Granger Cause GDP	32	0.68965	0.5104
GDP does not Granger Cause NREC		2.41745	0.1082
GFCF does not Granger Cause GDP	32	7.50129	0.0026
GDP does not Granger Cause GFCF		1.08304	0.3528
LFOR does not Granger Cause GDP	32	1.45058	0.2521
GDP does not Granger Cause LFOR		6.37134	0.0054

Source: Author's Estimation

Diagnostic Test

The series of residuals must be homoscedastic, normally distributed, and have no serial correlation. We used the VEC Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests to test for serial correlation, with the null hypothesis being H_0 : no serial correlation at lag order. Up to lag 2, our findings demonstrate that serial correlation is not present. The VEC Residual Normality Tests with Orthogonalization: Cholesky (Lutkepohl) were used to test the model's normality, and the results indicated that the series were jointly normally distributed. We used White VEC Residual Heteroskedasticity Tests to test heteroskedasticity. According to the test results, the series is homoscedastic. We also examined the model's stability, and all of the inverse roots in Figure 1 are contained within the unit circle, a model that is stable and passes every test run on the residuals, as indicated in Table 11.

Table: 11 Diagnostic Test

<i>Autocorrelation LM-Test</i>		
LM-Stat	Prob.	Conclusion
25.608	0.429	No serial autocorrelation
<i>White Heteroskedasticity Joint Test</i>		
Chi-sq	Prob.	Conclusion
340.406	0.335	No heteroskedasticity
<i>VEC Joint Residual Normality Tests</i>		
<i>Orthogonalization: Cholesky (Lutkepohl)</i>		
Jarque-Bera	Prob.	Conclusion
12.548	0.250	Residuals are normally distributed

Source: Author's Estimation

Figure: 1 Inverse Roots of AR Characteristic Polynomial

Conclusion

This study applied cointegration, VECM, and Granger causality techniques to explore both short-run and long-run dynamics among REC, NREC, LFOR, GFCF, and GDP from 1990 to 2023. A key strength of the research lies in the use of VECM, which allows a clearer understanding of how these macroeconomic variables interact over different time horizons. The findings reveal that in Pakistan, both renewable (REC) and non-renewable energy consumption (NREC) significantly contribute to long-run GDP growth. In contrast, labor force (LFOR) shows no meaningful influence, while gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) exerts a negative and statistically significant effect. The error correction term further suggests that about 5.4% of short-run adjustments in GDP move toward restoring long-run equilibrium.

Short-run analysis using the Wald test indicates that only GFCF exerts a significant influence on GDP, with no short-run linkage observed between GDP and energy consumption (REC, NREC) or LFOR. The Granger causality tests highlight a bidirectional causal relationship between GDP and REC, suggesting mutual

influence. Moreover, one-way causality runs from GFCF to GDP and from GDP to LFOR. However, no causal connection was found between GDP and NREC.

Notably, the Pakistani government and policymakers need to focus more on the country's present and upcoming energy issues and address the energy deficit. Private firms and Pakistani government representatives attempt to concentrate on creative ways to fund recoverable energy initiatives, particularly renewable energy, which will not only solve the country's energy problems but also benefit the environment. Furthermore, this study makes a few suggestions for future research, one of which is to do a comparable study over a longer time frame. It's also essential to incorporate other factors into the analysis, such as ICT, and use more sophisticated econometric models.

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